

A flexible toolkit for real-time action recognition of virtual humans in XR/AR environments

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Abstract—Real-time action recognition for virtual humans in XR/AR scenes is essential for creating natural and interactive experiences, allowing avatars or holoported humans to respond dynamically to user movements and gestures. This technology enhances applications such as immersive gaming, virtual training simulations and remote collaboration by enabling realistic character interactions and intuitive control. It is also valuable in healthcare and rehabilitation, where motion tracking can be used for physical therapy exercises and progress monitoring. Recognizing the need for robust action recognition in XR environments, we therefore present a flexible toolkit for real-time action recognition of virtual humans in XR environments. Our toolkit is built using Unity due to its widespread adoption and adaptability in XR/AR application development. The action recognition component leverages cutting-edge deep learning models to ensure high accuracy and performance and runs the analysis on a dedicated processing PC in order to not disrupt the smoothness of the XR experience. Preliminary experiments and evaluations show that the toolkit is able to recognize a variety of actions (like raising the hand, waving the hand or jumping) in a robust way.

Index Terms—real-time human action recognition, artificial intelligence, virtual humans, human-computer interaction, XR, Unity, real-time processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Real-time action (as well as gesture and emotion) recognition for virtual humans in XR/AR environments is crucial for creating immersive, interactive and responsive experiences. By accurately recognizing user actions and gestures in real time, virtual avatars and holoported humans can behave naturally, improving the sense of presence and realism in digital environments. This capability enables seamless human-computer interaction, allowing users to control avatars through body movements, engage in natural communication with virtual characters and experience adaptive responses based on their actions. In applications such as training simulations, remote collaboration and entertainment, real-time action recognition ensures that digital counterparts react appropriately, making interactions feel more intuitive and reducing the need for external controllers or manual input.

The applications of real-time action recognition in XR/AR are extensive, covering industries such as healthcare, gaming, education, and remote work. In medical training, it allows students to practice procedures with virtual patients who respond dynamically to their movements. In gaming

and entertainment, it enhances player immersion by enabling avatars to mimic real-world gestures accurately. For remote collaboration, holoported individuals can convey non-verbal cues effectively, making virtual meetings more lifelike and engaging. Additionally, in industrial training, workers can interact with augmented instructions through natural gestures, reducing cognitive load and improving learning efficiency. Overall, real-time action recognition is a key enabler for more natural and effective interactions in extended reality environments.

Motivated by these needs, we therefore present a flexible toolkit for real-time action recognition of virtual humans in XR environments, which will be described in the following. We designed the toolkit for *Unity* (in combination with the core action recognition running in Python), as Unity is the most popular and versatile framework for developing XR/AR applications. For the action recognition itself, we rely on state of the art deep learning based models.

The paper is organized as follows. In section II we describe related work and tools. Section III gives a high-level overview of our toolkit. The section IV describes in detail our *JrsVision* Unity package, which provides the key Unity components within the toolkit. In section V we describe the *Visual Analyzer*, our proposed action recognition method which is implemented in Python and delivers the results to Unity via the *JrsVision* components. Section VI gives information about the preliminary experiments and evaluations we performed with the proposed toolkit. Finally, section VII concludes the work and gives an outlook of our planned future work.

II. RELATED WORK

There is a lot of academic works and algorithms in the literature which deal with the topic of action recognition. Typical action recognition algorithms are vision-based (so with RGB video as input) and employ a complex chain of AI models (e.g. detection of human bounding boxes in the image, skeleton/pose estimation for detected humans, pose-based action recognition). For more information, we refer to the survey of action recognition algorithms given in [8] which provides a detailed review of the state of the art. Note that many of these algorithms are open-source, but usually invoked in an offline fashion (input video file as input) and of course not integrated in any way into an XR engine like Unity.

Fig. 1. Overview of the toolkit and its two main modules *JrsVision* and *Visual Analyzer*. The *JrsVision* Unity package has components for rendering a live video stream from the viewpoint of the observer camera and for receiving the detected actions. The *Visual Analyzer* does the action recognition using a combination of AI modules and returns the recognized actions.

Unity Sentis [5] is an Unity SDK that enables AI inference within Unity applications, allowing developers to integrate machine learning models into games, XR environments and real-time simulations. Neural network models trained in deep learning frameworks like PyTorch and Tensorflow can be used in Unity Sentis after converting them to the *ONNX* format. Unfortunately, as mentioned above the typical workflow for action recognition (and other high-level computer vision tasks) is not the inference of a single neural network. It involves a complex chain of multiple AI models which are combined together and includes also all sort of pre- and postprocessing steps in between. Furthermore, Unity Sentis runs the AI model inference always locally on the same device where Unity runs. Especially for large neural network models this can lead to increased CPU and GPU usage, thereby reducing the resources available for rendering and physics calculations. This can lower the frame rate due to dropped frames, which may disrupt the smoothness of the XR experience and increase the risk of motion sickness.

The *Mivry SDK* [4] is an Unity SDK for detection of hand gestures based on analysis of the 3D trajectory of the VR motion controllers. It allows to train custom hand gestures from a couple of motion controller movements recorded by the user. As the gesture recognition in the *Mivry SDK* is based on the analysis of the motion controller movement, it obviously does not work for humans which have been holoported into the scene via volumetric video. Furthermore, it is not able to detect complex actions which involve multiple virtual humans in the XR scene, for example two virtual humans which are hugging each other.

III. OVERVIEW OF THE TOOLKIT

We will first explain the different kind of characters who are interacting in XR environments. We will summarize all these different types with the term *virtual humans* and aim to recognize their actions. Firstly, *smart avatars* represent users wearing VR headsets, acting as their digital embodiment in the virtual world. These avatars mirror the user movements

and gestures, allowing natural interaction with the environment and other participants. *Holoported humans* are real persons which are captured through volumetric video and streamed into the XR scene, enabling realistic telepresence by preserving their full-body appearance and motion. Holoportation is particularly useful for remote collaboration, training and social interactions. Finally, *intelligent agents* are AI-powered virtual humans designed to interact autonomously with users and other virtual entities. These agents can simulate human-like behavior, respond to speech and gestures and perform tasks ranging from customer support to guiding users in training simulations. Together, all these virtual human types create diverse and dynamic XR experiences blending human presence with AI-driven interactions.

The high-level overview of our toolkit for real-time action recognition in XR scenes is illustrated in Figure 1. The toolkit contains two modules which are continuously exchanging data with each other, the *JrsVision* module and the *Visual Analyzer* module. The *JrsVision* module renders a live video stream from the viewpoint of the observer camera, receives the detected actions and matches them with the virtual humans in the scene. In contrast, the *Visual Analyzer* module does the actual action recognition for all virtual humans using a combination of AI modules and sends the result to the *JrsVision* module. The proposed design with a dedicated processing PC which invokes the core action recognition algorithm has the advantage that it does not consume significant CPU and GPU resources on the PC where the Unity XR scene is rendered and therefore ensures a smooth XR experience. The *Visual Analyzer* module invokes a complex chain of AI modules: Detection and tracking of virtual humans in the live video stream (created by the respective *JrsVision* component), skeleton/pose estimation for each detected virtual human and skeleton-based action recognition. The *Visual Analyzer* application is implemented in Python as it provides useful machine learning frameworks like *PyTorch*. More details about the *JrsVision* module can be found in section IV, whereas section V provides information about the *Visual Analyzer* module.

IV. JRSVISION

The JrsVision module is a novel Unity plugin which contains several components which are added to the Unity XR scene and exchange data with the Visual Analyzer module which does the actual action recognition. Specifically, the *Stream Camera Capture* component generates a low-latency video stream (MPEG-TS, H.264 codec) from the viewpoint of the observer camera, which is analyzed in real-time by the Visual Analyzer Python application. The *Collider Location History* component tracks the bounding box position of colliders attached to Unity game objects which are tagged as virtual humans, which helps to compensate for the input video stream latency during the matching step in the *Action Receiver* component. The *Listener Rest API* component handles the REST API calls (containing the detected actions) generated by the Visual Analyzer, while the *Action Receiver* component parses these messages to match the detected actions with the corresponding Virtual Human game objects in the Unity scene. In the following subsections, the involved JrsVision Unity components (which are illustrated in Figure 2) are described in a more detailed way.

In order to integrate real-time action recognition into the XR scene, some setup steps have to be done at the beginning. For all Unity game objects corresponding to a virtual human their tag has to be set to ‘VirtualHuman’. If the game object (for the virtual human) has not yet a collider set, then a collider (a simple box collider is fine) has to be attached to it. Furthermore, a new camera has to be added to the Unity scene, which serves as the ‘observer camera’. The video livestream will be rendered from the viewpoint of the observer camera and sent in realtime to the Visual Analyzer. For best performance of the action recognition algorithm, some guidelines for placing the observer camera should be taken into account. The observer camera should look approximately horizontally to the virtual humans in the scene (no camera tilt, no bird-eye view) and should be static. Furthermore, it should be positioned so that the virtual humans are always visible in this camera.

A. Stream Camera Capture

The Stream Camera Capture component generates a low-latency video stream (MPEG-TS via UDP) from the view of the Unity camera to which it is attached to. This live video stream is analyzed in real-time by the Visual Analyzer Python application. The component has configuration parameters for setting the desired resolution and the frame rate of the livestream which is created. Per default, a video livestream with a resolution of 1600x900 pixel is rendered with a rendering frame rate of 30 frames per second. The employed codec can be also set (with H.264 as the default) as well as the protocol and URL endpoint for the video livestream. We employ MPEG-TS as the container format and UDP as the transport protocol, as they are best suited¹ for low-latency video livestreams. We did experiments with different

¹<https://www.obe.tv/why-does-mpeg-ts-still-exist/>

Fig. 2. Illustration of the key components of the JrsVision module and their config parameters within the Unity Inspector window.

container formats and transport protocol, which showed that this combination gives the lowest latency of roughly 200 milliseconds. In contrast, when using RTSP we observed a latency of approximately three seconds, which is way too high for real-time action recognition.

The implementation of the Stream Camera Capture component is based on the respective component of the *FFmpegOut* open-source package². It captures the current image content from the viewpoint of the observer camera regularly (default is 30 times per second) and renders it into a render texture

²<https://github.com/fh-joanneum-research-and-design-lab/FFmpegOut/tree/live-streaming>

Fig. 3. Illustration of successfully detected actions for different kinds of virtual humans (left one is a holoported person, whereas the middle and right one are intelligent agents).

buffer. The current render texture is then encoded and sent to the video livestream via a subprocess which utilizes the *FFMPEG* executable (*FFMPEG* is an open source toolkit³ for encoding/decoding multimedia data). We optimized the *ffmpeg* encoding parameters for minimum latency as specified in⁴. We employ the *H.264* codec due to its flexibility and high compression ability. The *FFMPEG* toolkit provides both a software implementation (on the CPU) as well as a hardware implementation (for *NVIDIA* GPUs) of the *H.264* codec.

B. Collider Location History

The Collider Location History component calculates the 2D bounding box positions of the colliders which have been attached to Unity game objects with tag 'VirtualHuman' (corresponding to the virtual humans in the scene) and keeps them up over the last few seconds. This data is necessary for the subsequent matching step in the Action Receiver component, as even with a low-latency MPEG-TS video stream there will be still be input video stream latency of approximately 200 milliseconds.

The calculation of the 2D bounding box for a certain collider is done as follows. For the collider, first all eight corner points of its bounding volume (rectangle) in world coordinates are retrieved. These corner points are then projected from world coordinates to normalized 2D screen space and the smallest 2D bounding box is calculated which contains all eight projected corner points.

³<https://www.ffmpeg.org/>

⁴<https://stackoverflow.com/questions/42953616/very-low-latency-streaming-with-ffmpeg-using-a-webcam>

C. Listener Rest Api

The Listener Rest Api component implements a REST Service which handles the REST calls (REST messages) generated by the Visual Analyzer Python application, which contain the metadata with the recognized actions for all virtual humans. It creates a simple HTTP protocol listener object and polls periodically (every 20 milliseconds by default) for incoming REST PUT calls and parses them.

D. Action Receiver

The Action Receiver component parses the received REST messages which contains the detected actions for the virtual humans) and matches them with the Virtual Human game objects in the Unity scene. The metadata stored in the Collider Location History component is also important and is taken into account correspondingly. The matching assumes that a certain input frame delay for the Visual Analyzer is present (due to encoding and subsequent decoding of the frame, transmission of the UDP packets in the network etc.) and adjusts the calculation accordingly. By default, an input frame delay of 200 milliseconds is assumed. After matching, the action information for all Virtual Human game object is provided in a global dictionary.

E. Action Info Listener

We provide also a callback-based interface via the Action Info Listener component. It has to be attached to the Virtual Human game object for which the action recognition shall be done and provides the action for this virtual human via a callback function.

Fig. 4. Screenshot of the action recognition toolkit and an Unity instance playing the XR scene in the Unity editor, here with both modules of the toolkit (JrsVision and Visual Analyzer) running on the same PC. One can see that the action ‘raise hand’ is recognized correctly by the Visual Analyzer and subsequently returned to the Unity instance, where it is overlaid onto the virtual human to which the detected action corresponds.

V. VISUAL ANALYZER

The Visual Analyzer is a Python application which does the processing of the input video stream received from Unity in multiple steps. First, all virtual humans are detected with a deep learning based object detector and tracked with an optical flow based method. In parallel, for all detected humans their 2D pose (skeleton) is calculated with a deep learning based pose estimation algorithm. The actions of all virtual humans are now calculated with a deep learning based action recognition algorithm from the trajectory of its 2D poses within an analysis period of roughly two seconds. All detected actions are then sent back via REST API to the PC where Unity runs. In the following, we provide more details on the individual processing steps.

In the first step of the processing pipeline, virtual humans in the video stream are detected and tracked using the *Scaled-YoloV4* object detector [6] and *TV-L1* optical flow [7]. Both run on the GPU via CUDA and utilize multithreading, enabling real-time performance at 25 milliseconds per frame. Next, 2D human poses (skeletons) are estimated using the deep learning based algorithm *RTMPose* [2], which detects 17 keypoints per skeleton. We use the *RTMPose-m* variant for a balance of speed and accuracy, running in a separate process for efficiency. The

pose estimation takes roughly 8 – 10 milliseconds per virtual human, allowing real-time processing for up to five virtual humans in the XR scene.

For skeleton-based action recognition, we use a deep learning based approach which analyzes the 2D pose trajectories of a certain virtual human over an analysis period of roughly two seconds and returns the detected action. We employ *PoseConv3D* [1], a state of the art algorithm that detects the 60 actions (like clapping, waving, jump, pickup) trained on the *NTU-60*⁵ dataset. *PoseConv3D* utilizes a 3D CNN on pose heatmaps instead of the usual graph-based neural networks, which has the advantage of improved spatiotemporal feature learning, robustness to pose estimation noise and better generalization. We employ the model available via the *MMAction2* machine learning package⁶. The inference with the *PoseConv3D* model takes roughly 45 milliseconds for each virtual human. Initial experiments on several XR Unity scenes recordings with different types of virtual humans demonstrate that their actions can be detected robustly, as can be seen in Figure 3.

⁵<https://rose1.ntu.edu.sg/dataset/actionRecognition>

⁶<https://github.com/open-mmlab/mmaaction2>

All runtime numbers are measured on a Windows PC with a NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU, and all employed neural networks are processed on the GPU.

VI. PRELIMINARY EXPERIMENTS AND EVALUATION

Preliminary qualitative and latency tests of the proposed toolkit for real-time action recognition have been performed with multiple Unity XR/AR scenes involving different types of virtual humans - smart avatars, holoported humans and intelligent agents. As shown in Figures 3 and 4, the qualitative evaluation indicates that the toolkit is able to recognize actions like ‘raise hand’ and several others (like waving hand, arm swing or throwing something) robustly for all virtual humans in the scene. Furthermore, the smoothness of the XR experience is not negatively impacted, as the actual action recognition (which is computationally expensive as it invokes several neural network models) is done on a separate processing PC.

Due to the low-latency encoding (via MPEG-TS over UDP) and decoding of the rendered video livestream it is assured that the Visual Analyzer receives the video live stream with minimum latency. The overall latency for detecting an action is roughly two seconds, which is not significantly higher than the time a human needs for recognizing a certain action. It could be further reduced by decreasing the analysis period (the time interval for which the poses of the virtual human are analyzed), but this might have a negative impact on the detection accuracy of the action recognition.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work we present a flexible toolkit for real-time action recognition of virtual humans in XR environments, addressing the need for natural and interactive experiences. Built with Unity for its adaptability in XR/AR development, the toolkit employs advanced deep learning models to ensure high accuracy while running on a dedicated processing PC to maintain a smooth XR experience. Preliminary evaluations demonstrate its ability to robustly recognize various actions, making it a valuable tool for applications such as gaming, training, remote collaboration and healthcare.

In the future, we will do a quantitative evaluation of the action recognition algorithm (accuracy, recall etc.) as well as a more detailed analysis of its runtime and latency. Additionally, we plan to extend the core algorithm for action recognition with additional neural network models for emotion recognition, by analyzing the face of the virtual human. Furthermore, we will add vision-language models like *Video-LLaVA* [3] in order to recognize complex social interactions between multiple virtual humans (e.g., two virtual humans are having an argument with each other) in the scene.

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